

A Comparative Study On The Financial Performance of Public Sector Bank & Private Sector Bank in India

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Abstract -

Banking sector is one of the fastest growing sectors in India. Today's banking sector becoming more complex. The objective of this study is to analyze the Financial Position and Performance of the Public Sector Bank (State bank of India, Bank of India, and Punjab National Bank) and Private Sector Bank (AXIS, ICICI, HDFC) in India. In this research, we will study we study three public sector banks and three private sector banks. The expected result from the study there is that the financial performance or financial position of one in three banks affects the public sector and the private sector as well. And later a public sector bank and a private sector bank compare among themselves that the net profit and branches of which bank sector is better than the other.

Keyword – SBI, BOI, PNB, AXIS, ICICI, HDFC, Financial Position, Performance, Net Profit, Branches

Introduction:-

Banks assume a vital part inside the financial improvement of a country. As the banking business is an important financial sector of the India economy. Indian banking business have been running and working successfully and increasing growth of Indian economy. The Banking sector is one of the necessary parts of the monetary framework. This sector gives monetary administrations not exclusively to the business yet additionally to the agribusiness and family areas. It additionally plays significant job in line of capital in the economy. India Banking sector has an incredible commitment in the financial development of the country. Reserve Bank of India (RBI) is the apex body of the Indian Banking sector. The Reserve Bank of India has been distributing concentrates on the financial execution of Indian confidential corporate business area for the beyond seventy years. The examinations were embraced so as to catch the patterns in income, value of production, sales, productivity, saving, investment, borrowings, and so on, in the confidential corporate business area. It guarantees the steadiness in the money related arrangement of the country. Since independence, RBI has started a few measures to work on more admittance to monetary administrations through monetary training, awareness and technological up degrees in a reasonable way. Public sector banks are the banks where the public authority has a significant holding. Private sector banks are those banks wherein the value is held by private investors, i.e., there is no administration shareholding. Public sector banks overwhelmed the Indian banking industry in the underlying stages. Monetary area changes rolled out numerous improvements in financial industry and private sector bank manages an account with the assistance of cutting edge innovation and

professionalized administration accomplished a difficult position subsequently making an incredible danger the public sector banks.

The performance of the banking sector should be an essential monetary dynamic of Indian economy. Thus, the changes in banking sector are planned to make the banks more effective. however, the Banking sector is confronting disturbing difficulties like ascending in rivalry, level of Non-Performing Assets and weakening asset quality. These may adversely affect the economy of the country.

Literature Review :- (Karri, Meghani, & Mishra, 2015) The work in this paper is focusing on financial position of Bank of Baroda and Punjab National Bank. We have chosen the CAMEL model and t-test which measures the performance of bank from each of the important parameter like capital adequacy, asset quality, management efficiency, earning quality, liquidity and Sensitivity. Bank of Baroda and Punjab National Bank have succeeded in maintaining CRAR at a higher level than the prescribed level, 10%. But the Bank of Baroda has maintained highest across the duration of last five years. It is very good sign for the banks to survive and to expand in future. Out of 14 ratios used in the CAMEL model the average figures of Bank Of Baroda is the best for (6 ratios) followed by Punjab National Bank (5 ratios). Thus it is established that Bank of Baroda is the best bank in the selected public sector banks.

(Padma & Arulmathi, 2013) This Study Focusing on State Bank of India and ICICI Bank. Performance and efficiency of Commercial Bank, the study set out to apply Profitability ratios, Solvency ratios and Management efficiency ratios on SBI and ICICI Bank. State Bank of India (SBI) and ICICI Bank are the two largest banks in India in public and private sector. According to the analysis,

both the banks are maintaining the required standards and running profitably. The comparison of the performance of SBI and ICICI Bank indicates that there is a significant difference between the performance of SBI and ICICI Bank in terms of Deposits, Advances, Investments, Net Profit, and Total Assets. It is inferred that SBI has an extensive operation than ICICI Bank. **(Balaji & Kumar, 2016)** The study is to analyze and compare the overall financial performance of selected public and private sector banks in India and net income, operating profit, net profit also study. Total incomes of both public and private sector banks recorded a good growth in total income during all the years of study. Net interest income is showing an increasing trend for both sectors. Net interest margin for public sector banks is quantitatively high. The volume of operating profit for public sector banks is much higher than the private sector banks. A shifting momentum from public sector to private sector has been recorded in case of net profit. Public sector banks recorded for the maximum volume of net profit in the first two years of study. Private sector banks continuously recorded well profits for all the years compare to private sector banks.

(Koley, 2019) The present study is made to measure the financial position, performance and efficiency of the largest public sector bank (SBI) and private sector bank (HDFC). The CAMEL model has been used to assess the financial strength of the selected banks. The capital and capital adequacy ratio for both the banks are more than Basel norms for bank. So, they are satisfactory for both SBI and HDFC banks. The net NPA to net advance ratio is higher for SBI than HDFC. It can be concluded that efficiency in management of advances given to customers are not good for SBI. Net profit ratio is also high for HDFC bank. So, HDFC has a better profitability and better management efficiency than SBI.

(Chaudhary & Sharma, 2011) This paper attempts to analyze how efficiently Public and Private sector banks have been managing NPA. It is right time to take suitable and stringent measures to get rid of NPA problem. An efficient management information system should be developed. The bank staff involved in sanctioning the advances should be trained about the proper documentation and charge of securities and motivated to take measures in preventing advances turning into NPA. Public banks should focus on their working to contend private banks. Banks ought to be well knowledgeable in legitimate choice of borrower/project and in investigating the budget summary.

(Jha, 2018) This Study Focusing on two major bank, that is Punjab National Bank (PNB) and Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India (ICICI). The Punjab national bank (PNB) is one of the second largest public sector banks after

SBI (state bank of India) and ICICI (Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India) is one of the largest private sector banks in India. The study reveals that bank customers have high trust in public sector banks as compared to private sector banks. People preferred PNB bank to require loans and advances as compare to ICICI bank. However, PNB bank has lower operational efficiency comparatively than ICICI bank.

(Gupta, 2014) Banking Sector plays an important role in economic development of a country. The banking system of India is featured by a large network of bank branches, serving many kinds of financial services of the people Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India (ICICI) Bank today is a leading player in Indian banking industry and is deeply engaged in human and economic development at the national level. The NPAs of the ICICI bank is more than one per cent, hence should control NPAs otherwise it affects the asset quality in long run. Proper control over leverage should be taken in order to magnify DP ratio. The spread of the ICICI bank should control otherwise the income of the bank is eaten away by the interest expenses in the long-run.

(Haque, 2014) In This Era, the banking sector is one of the fastest growing sectors, and a lot of funds are channelized through banks thereby making the banking system more and more complex wherein lies the importance to examine and evaluate concurrent performance of the banks: hence the researcher tries to present a case study of India in this context. To evaluate the performance of the Indian banks, the researcher has opted to compare the financial performance of different Scheduled Commercial Banks (SCBs) applying the parameters— Return on Asset, Return on Equity and Net Interest Margin. The financial performance of different banking groups in terms of profitability has been evaluated and appraised based on different ratios like ROA, ROE and NIM. The outcomes demonstrate that most of the banking groups have witnessed a downturn performance in terms of ROA from 2009 to 2010. For Public Sector Banks it is recorded 0.97% in 2010 against 1.02% in 2009. ROA of the SBI group is also a notch lower at 0.91% 2010 than 1.02% during the previous year.

(Lyngdoh, 2018) Indian Banking system has played an important role in the financial development of India. RBI, the regulatory authority of the banking system in India includes public sector banks, private sector banks, financial and non-financial institutions. The banking system of India comprises of an extensive network of bank offices the nation over which serves the people by providing various financial services. The purpose of the study is to examine the financial performance of the top two largest banks in the India, one from public sector banks and other from private sector banks in India,

SBI and HDFC Bank. The study found that the mean value of credit deposit ratio was higher in SBI (84.08%) as compared to that in HDFC Bank (82.50%) during the 5 year period (2012-13 to 2016-17). Hence, on the basis of the above study and analysis it is shown that banking customer has more preference and trust on SBI as it has a larger customer base than HDFC Bank. However, it is also seen that HDFC Bank has a faster growth which means that, it is more efficient in operations than SBI.

(Rajendran & Sudha, 2019) This study has been carried out to evaluate the financial performance of HDFC Bank. HDFC was amongst the first to receive an 'in principle' approval from the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) to set up a bank in the private sector. The bank at present has an enviable network of over 4,805 branches spread over cities across India. All branches are linked on an online real time basis. Customers in over 500 locations are also servicing through telephone banking. The bank also has a network of about over 12,860 networked ATMs 2,657 across cities and towns. The HDFC Bank is the largest private sector bank in India. The researcher find the financial performance for the past five financial years from 2014-15 to 2018-19. The data collected from annual reports of the bank and the web site. The data analyzed through various ratios. This research article finally concluded that the HDFC bank financial performance is strong during the study period.

(Rao & Ibrahim, 2017) Indian Banking industry is led by public sector banks (PSBs) with 80 percent market share. The present study is to compare the financial performance of IDBI Bank with the industry averages on the basis of financial ratios for the period 2011-12 to 2015-16. The solvency position of IDBI Bank and the employment of assets are in tune with the industry averages. The employment of shareholders' funds and the CASA which is relatively lower than the bellwether suggests that attention has to be paid in these areas. Net profit margin of IDBI Bank indicates that the profits of the bank is declining and is well below the industry averages suggesting that the operations of the bank has to improve.

(Srinivasan & Saminathan, 2016) Camel approach is significant tool to assess the relative financial strength of a bank and to suggest necessary measures to improve weaknesses of a bank. In India, RBI adopted this approach in 1996 followed on the recommendations of Padmanabham Working Group (1995) committee. In the present study, an attempt has been made to rank the various commercial banks operating in India. The banks in India have been categorized into Public sector, Private sector, and Foreign banks. The sample of selected banks consists of 25 Public

Sector, 18 Private Sector, and 8 Foreign banks. For the purpose of ranking, CAMEL MODEL approach has been applied, incorporating important parameters like Capital Adequacy, Assets Quality, Management Efficiency, Earnings Quality and Liquidity. The finding of the study shows that public sector banks, viz. Andhra Bank, Bank of Baroda, Allahabad Bank, Punjab National Bank IDBI Bank, State Bank of Bikaner and Jaipur and UCO Bank has been ranked at the top five positions in their financial performance during the study period. The private sector banks, namely, Tamilnad Merchantile Bank, Kotak Mahindra Bank, HDFC Bank, Axis Bank, Karur Vysya Bank, ICICI Bank, Citi Union Bank and IndusInd Bank shared the top five positions. The foreign banks such as Bank of Bahrain & Kuwait, HSBC Bank, The Royal Bank of Scotland, Deutsche Bank, CTBS Bank, Citi Bank, DBS Bank and Royal Bank of Scotland secured the top five positions during the study period. The empirical results show that there is a statistically significant difference between the CAMEL ratios of the selected Public Sector Banks, Private Sector Banks and Foreign Banks in India.

(Srivastava, 2021) In Indian banking sector is a combination of public, private, and foreign banks. Private Banks play a vital role in the Indian economy. They in directly motivate the public sector banks by offering healthy competition to them. In India, the private sector banks consist of three categories: Private Scheduled Banks, Private Non-Scheduled Banks, and Foreign Banks. The study deals with analyzing the financial performance of private sector banks HDFC and ICICI bank in India. According to the top listed private sector banks, HDFC and ICICI bank plays a vital role in a wide range of banking products and financial services. Based on the analysis, the study concludes that HDFC bank performance is comparatively better than the ICICI bank. HDFC Bank and ICICI bank are the largest private sector banks in India. By the analysis, the financial performance of HDFC bank is financially sound when compared to ICICI bank. The results of hypothesis testing show that total income and total expenses have a significant difference in ICICI bank. When compared to the financial performance based on Advances, Deposits, Borrowings, and Investments, there is a significant difference in the financial performance of HDFC bank. Hence the study concludes that HDFC bank performance is comparatively better than the ICICI bank.

(Mustafa & Taqi) Banks play an important role in the economic development of a country. They are the lifeblood of modern commerce and have control over a large part of money supply. A bank is a financial intermediary that accepts deposits and channels them into lending activities. It plays a vital role in the marketing of new type of deposits and

advances schemes. The financial performance of a bank can be measured as the achievement of the bank in terms of profitability position, service quality, customer satisfaction and other relevant aspects. In such a scenario, the present study is an attempt to measure the financial performance of the second largest public sector bank of India i.e. Punjab National Bank. This study is entirely based on secondary data and different ratios have been applied to evaluate the financial performance of the bank along with regression analysis with the help of SPSS 20.0. The study concluded that the selected bank has performed well on the sources of growth rate and financial efficiency but profitability position has been found poor during the study period. The present study aimed to measure the financial performance of Punjab National Bank from 2011-12 to 2015-16. Punjab National Bank is a major public sector bank of India which plays an important role in the development of Indian financial system. The financial viability of the banking system is certainly essential; not only to instill public confidence but also to make banks capable of discharging their social responsibilities. The Punjab National Bank of India is in a position to follow the rules of the Government for the social and economic development of the country. The bank has performed well on the sources of growth rate and financial efficiency during the study period. It plays a vital role in marketing of new type of deposits and advances schemes. However, the bank, by earning at least a nominal profit, have to serve the economy

through extension of advances and safeguard the interest of its investors by providing the expected return on their investment in bank. **(Adhana & Gulati, 2019)** The present study is conducted to compare the financial performance of Axis Bank and ICICI Bank on the basis of Net Profit and some ratios such as return on equity, capital adequacy, Total Income to Capital Employed and Total Debt to Owners Fund ratio etc. The period of study taken is from the year 2013-14 to 2017-18. The study found that ICICI Bank is performing well and financially sound in terms of Net profit than Axis Bank but in context of return on equity Axis Bank has better managing efficiency than ICICI Bank. The study shows that the ICICI Bank is performing very well in terms of earning net profit over the last five years as compared to Axis Bank. Every year ICICI Bank is ahead of its competitor Axis Bank. In 2017-18 ICICI bank is earning huge profit of 6777.44 crore rupees as compared to 275.68 crore rupees of Axis Bank. Out of six Sub- hypotheses tested, in two hypotheses Alternative gets selected and Null gets rejected. And in other four hypotheses Null is selected and the Alternative is rejected.

Expected outcome of this Research Paper

We study three public sector banks and three private sector banks. The expected result from the study there is that the net profit and branches of one in three banks affects the public sector and the private sector as well.

PUBLIC SECTOR BANK

Year	State Bank of India		Bank of India		Punjab National Bank	
	Branches	Net Profit	Branches	Net Profit	Branches	Net Profit
2018-19	22010	862 Cr.	5092	55469005	6989	9975 Cr.
2019-20	22141	14488 Cr	5119	29568862	7040	336 Cr.
2020-21	22219	20410 Cr.	5107	21602987	10769	2022 Cr.

PRIVATE SECTOR BANK

Year	AXIS		ICICI		HDFC	
	Branches	Net Profit	Branches	Net Profit	Branches	Net Profit
2018-19	4050+	4677 Cr.	4874	33633016	1350	21078 Cr.
2019-20	4500+	1627 Cr.	5324	79308124	1468+	26257.3 Cr.
2020-21	4594	6588 Cr.	5266	161926841	5608	31116.5 Cr.

Conclusion

The main objective of this paper is to evaluate the financial performance as well as compare the performance of selected public sector banks and

private sector banks in India. As we know that banks are the backbone of any economy. This research will know the financial performance public sector bank and private sector bank in India's bank,

which will help us to running of India's Banks.

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